

Regression Analysis of Foreign Direct Investment on Employment Creation in Nigeria

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

FDI is very important for countries to reduce their rates of unemployment. Therefore, knowledge on foreign direct investment, economic growth, government revenue, increased tax, and living standard and its application will help determine its success on employment creation in every economy. The paper examines the impact of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) on employment creation in Nigeria. The study was exploratory research, which was conducted using a survey design. Valid sample adequacy of 292 respondents was employed. We conducted a comprehensive investigation to determine the impact of each variable on employment. During the statistical analysis, we employed the multiple linear regression model and ANOVA test to establish the significant impact of the explanatory variables (foreign direct investment, economic growth, government revenue, increased tax, and living standard) on employment. Our test results suggest that hypotheses (H1, H2, H3, and H4) have established the following results: Foreign direct investment is statistically not significant on employment creation. Economic growth is not statistically significant in employment creation. Government revenue generation through foreign direct investment does not impact positively on employment creation and an increase in tax revenue does not impact positively on employment creation respectively. The test result is an indication that foreign direct investment received into the Nigerian economy is not impacting significantly on employment creation. However, H5 statistically established that whenever employment is created it will affect living standards positively. This indicates that a percentage change in employment creation will lead to a positive change or increase in the living standards of the people. A negative reverse of this result will widen the unemployment gap in the country which will consequently affect the living standard of the populace. The research is an important contribution to the existing knowledge on FDI. The application of these research findings will serve as a guide and the need to appropriately channel the foreign direct inflows received into employment creation to ease or close the unemployment gap in Nigeria. This is a means of boosting the economic growth and prosperity of nations.

Keywords: FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT, EMPLOYMENT CREATION, ECONOMIC GROWTH, NIGERIA.

Introduction

A cross-border transaction in which a direct investor obtains a long-term interest in a direct investment firm is defined as foreign direct investment (Tang & Gyasi, 2012). A great number of studies have been conducted on the influence of FDI on economic growth, with mixed results. Capital inflows, labor force expansion, and technological innovation, according to neoclassical theory, will contribute to economic development in the host country. The vast majority of empirical studies suggest that FDI promotes economic development (Aust, Morais, & Pinto, 2020). While the majority of studies reveals a positive relationship between FDI and income growth, other authors argue that FDI can have detrimental consequences, particularly in the areas of social and environmental development. Research by (Ojeaburu, 2019) have claimed that the free movement of goods and services (trade flows) could help to alleviate unemployment, particularly in developing countries. Increased worker earnings have had a positive impact on economic growth, resulting in increased local demand, which helps to long-term GDP growth and lessens the risk of over-reliance on volatile overseas markets (Wheeler & Mody, 1992).

Nigeria is the most populous country on the continent. There is a considerable supply of surplus labor in the country. Nigeria's labor market is dualistic, with official and informal employment coexisting, with agriculture accounting for the majority of the country's workers, particularly at the subsistence level (Adesina, 2013). In general, Nigeria, like many other countries around the world, has recognized that, after education, the second most important form of empowerment that a state can provide to its citizens is to provide them with profitable employment, and as a result, successive governments have incorporated one form or another of an employment policy into their programs. Employment is a major issue for Nigeria, as it is for every economy, which is why one of every economy's macroeconomic goals is to achieve a high or full employment rate. The goal of creating employment, among other macroeconomic objectives, is crucial in many emerging countries, where unemployment and underuse of resources have resulted in rising poverty rates. Some analysts believe that, in order to boost employment, the movement of goods and services (trade flows) should be expedited, especially in developing countries (Bräutigam, 2011). However, creating jobs remains a huge difficulty for the Nigerian government (Obadan & Odusola, 2000). According to the (WB, 1999) Nigeria's employment creation has lagged behind the country's rising workforce. Because FDI is regarded as a driver of employment, technical progress, productivity increases, and eventually economic growth, determining the expected impact of FDI inflows on job creation in Nigeria is critical. Because FDI is regarded as a driver of employment, technical progress, productivity increases, and ultimately economic growth, establishing the link between FDI and job creation has become critical. It also aids emerging countries in bridging the gap between growth, foreign exchange, investment, and tax revenue. The advantage of FDI is that it allows industrialized countries to begin improving emerging market opportunities. Increasing profits, developing ties, and increasing market influence can help the poor world, whereas boosting earnings, developing relationships, and increasing market influence can help the developed world. The drawback of a foreign direct investment, on the other hand, is the risk

associated. A dividend-paying investment does not ensure that it will continue to pay dividends in the future. Because the global political backdrop is essentially brittle, a company's investment could be lost as soon as it is created if a seizure or takeover occurs, which could have a detrimental influence on job creation and the implications that come with it.

Problem statement

Given that poverty levels are frequently high, domestic savings and income are low, and income is largely allocated to consumption expenditure, the role of FDI in Africa is critical. These factors, combined with the unpredictability of foreign aid flows, Africa's limited share of global trade, and the high volatility of short-term capital movements, demand attracting a diverse range of FDI inflows. Given the value of foreign direct investment, West African countries must learn how to attract more of this precious resource. As a result, the majority of African countries have taken significant steps to encourage FDI by enacting FDI-specific legislative frameworks to support their investment objectives. In 1998, 45 of Africa's 53 countries developed FDI-specific regulatory frameworks, according to UNCTAD. The establishment of investment promotion organizations and facilities, as well as targeted investment programs. People, on the other hand, continue to struggle with employment-related concerns.

Research objectives

The main objective of this study is to examine the impact of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) on employment creation in Nigeria. The specific objectives of the research are;

1. To find out whether foreign direct investment influences employment creation.
2. To find out whether economic growth affects employment creation.
3. To find out whether Government revenue generation through foreign direct investment impacts employment creation.
4. To find out whether an increase in tax revenue affects employment creation.
5. To find out whether employment creation affects living standards.

Hypothesis

H1: Foreign direct investment is statistically not significant on employment creation (at $p (.659) > 0.05$)

H2: Economic growth is not statistically significant on employment creation (at $p (0.425) > 0.05$)

H3: Government revenue generation through foreign direct investment does not impact positively on employment creation (at $p (0.831) > 0.05$)

H4: Increased in tax revenue does not impact positively on employment creation (at $p (0.988) > 0.05$)

H5: Employment creation positively affects living standards at $p (0.00) < 0.05$.

Significance of the research

This research work is for policy formulation on foreign direct investment and sensitization of people on the effect of FDI in the country's economy and the possible demerits of FDI.

Fig.1 Conceptual framework

Source: Author's Construct, (2021)

The profile of the study area

The goal of this research is to find out how foreign direct investments affect employment in Nigeria. Nigeria is situated on Africa's western coast. The following is a rough map of the study's location:

Fig.2 Map of Nigeria

Source: Author's Construct, (2021)

The above diagram shows a clear connection between foreign direct investment and job creation. Conceptually, the foreign direct investment will directly impact employment, tax obligation, and revenue generation and consequently affect the living standards of the people.

Related theoretical basis and literature review

We looked at numerous economic theories, including the Classical theory of employment, investment theories, and the Keynesian theory of employment, while evaluating the literature (Keynes, 1937). However, the Keynesian theory of employment is chosen over the others among these ideas. According to Keynes, the region's aggregate effective demand for commodities determines the level of employment in the short term. The higher the aggregate efficient demand, the higher the employment volume, and vice versa. Unemployment, according to Keynes, is caused by a lack of effective demand. Effective demand insufficiency is caused by the income-to-consumption disparity. The gap can be addressed by raising investment and hence effective demand to retain employment at a high level (Keynes, 1937).

Foreign direct investment

Foreign direct investment (FDI) is defined by the United Nations as an investment in a company that is based in one nation but is “effectively controlled” by inhabitants of another (UNCTAD., 1991). Research conducted

by (Tang & Gyasi, 2012), described FDI as a cross-border investment in which a direct investor acquires a permanent interest in a direct investment company.

Also, (Oyero, 2019), a foreign direct investment is an investment made to acquire a permanent management interest (usually at least 10% of the voting stock) and at least 10% of the shareholding in an enterprise operating in a country other than the investor's home country. About (Omankhanlen, 2011), Foreign direct investment (FDI) is defined as a source of external resources such as technology, management and marketing knowledge, as well as money. All of these factors have a significant impact on the productive capacity of the host country, and the government's ability to regulate an adequate amount of FDI consisting of managerial, capital, and technological resources to boost the current production potential is largely dependent on its ability to regulate an adequate amount of FDI consisting of managerial, capital, and technological resources to boost the current production potential. Given this, (Wei, 2013b) a corporation or individual from one country investing in commercial interests in another country is defined as foreign direct investment (FDI).

Employment

The term "employment" has a wide range of connotations. Employment is a contractually based cooperative relationship between two people, one of whom is the employer and the other is the employee. It can alternatively be defined as environments in which able-bodied men and women who are eligible to work in any given society can easily find positions in which they will not be exploited throughout the hiring process and will be able to optimize their marginal labor production. The employment to population ratio (+15), which is the working-age population as a percentage of the total population, can also refer to the number of people aged 15 and up who are gainfully employed. It refers to people who are at least 15 years old and work for a living. The employment rate is calculated by dividing the total number of people in the labor force by the number of people who are employed. Full employment does not indicate that no one is unemployed; rather, it refers to the level of employment that occurs when the unemployment rate is normal, accounting for both frictional and structural factors (Nattrass & Seekings, 2018).

Unemployment

Unemployment is defined as a situation in which people who are willing and able to work are unable to do so due to a lack of job opportunities. According to (Ozughalu & Ogwumike, 2013), Unemployment is defined as a scenario in which people are ready and able to work at the present wage rate but are unable to do so because of financial constraints. According to (Ozughalu & Ogwumike, 2013), The taxonomy of unemployment, a state of unemployment, a job-seeking activity, a desire for a job under specific circumstances, and the need for a job are all covered. This means that certain requirements must be satisfied before a person can collect unemployment benefits. Individuals who are now unemployed yet willing and able to work for pay are currently available to work and actively seeking employment.

Empirical studies on the relationship between FDI and employment growth

FDI helps to increase the quantity and quality of jobs available. Unemployment is a big problem in developing countries. As a result, the employment generation effect of FDI is crucial for countries to reduce their unemployment rates. According to a (UNCTAD., 1991), The United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) has found that the bulk of FDI from developed countries to developing economies is capital- or technology-intensive, and that it has a crowding-out effect on recipient countries' economies. Some researchers determined that FDI had a positive impact on employment after analyzing the relationship between FDI and employment, whereas others disagree. The following is a more detailed examination of this issue of debate.

Again, (Mpanju, 2012), The ordinary least squares (OLS) approach to statistical model design and analysis was used to study the relationship between employment as the dependent variable and FDI as the independent variable in Tanzania. His findings found a clear positive relationship between the two variables, implying that higher FDI inflows are associated with higher employment (Nunnenkamp & Bremont, 2007) The relationship between foreign direct investment (FDI) and employment statistics from approximately 200 Mexican industrial businesses was investigated. They discovered that FDI had a significant positive impact on manufacturing employment, albeit in a limited way. Both white-collar and blue-collar jobs were affected by their findings. When crowding-out is taken into consideration, however, some studies indicate that the impact of FDI on employment is insignificant. When foreign multinational businesses concentrate on the market of the recipient country, the crowding-out impact is significant. The crowding-out effect of FDI will result in the bankruptcy of more domestic firms and the layoff of more local employees because FDI will put more pressure on domestic firms, and because advanced technologies and higher productivity associated with foreign investment will require fewer workers than before (Ajibola, Isiaka, Ogunleye, & Adeyemi, 2019). According to him, the impact of foreign direct investment on employment in European countries varies depending on the country's economic development stage, making it difficult to anticipate the outcome. He assumed that the first-level impact of FDI on employment was marked by creative destruction, suggesting that unproductive jobs would go as new and more productive occupations arose. There is a lot of competition created by the capitalism process and the transition from a controlled to a market economy. International investors modified their production mode before local firms in order to make more money. It was positioned by (Wang, 2002) As a result of this strategy, worldwide firms have a more productive workforce. The ruling class and managers began to restrict workers, and enterprises began to rely on computers. More jobs are created subsequently as a result of labor-intensive investment, transforming creative destruction into a positive employment impact. Furthermore, according to (Dufaux, 2010), Greenfield investment has a good impact on jobs, although brownfield investment has a limited positive impact on employment when linked with the privatization trend that generates a dynamic market economy. This study demonstrates that FDI is not a panacea for employment creation. More so, (Ernst, 2005b), since the 1990s, researchers have discovered that FDI has had minimal effect on employment in Latin American countries since it drives out small and medium-sized local businesses and creates mass unemployment in

domestic businesses.. However, (Wei, 2013b) It has been demonstrated that FDI has a favorable impact on the service sector. They classified FDI into three categories: resource-seeking FDI, efficiency-seeking FDI, and market-seeking FDI, and contrasted the international mobility costs of FDI producers and users to assess the effects of FDI on employment. Market-seeking FDI will dominate the local labor market and have a neutral or positive impact if customers are immobile or have significant transportation costs," they concluded. If users' mobility costs are low, FDI-seeking resources and productivity will take priority, wreaking havoc on the domestic labor market.

Economic growth

Economic growth, according to the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (Unctad, 2006b), is defined as an increase in production without a change in institutional or technological arrangements. Economic growth according to (Ozughalu & Ogwumike, 2013) is a quantitative and long-term increase in a country's per-capital production or revenue, accompanied by an increase in the labor force, consumption, capital, and trade volume. Hence, a long-term transformation that's induced by a gradual increase in savings and population rates (Rizvi & Nishat, 2009). Economic growth is seen by (Ajibola et al., 2019) as the potential growth of a country's GDP or national output He goes on to define it as the movement of a country's productive frontier outward. We can conclude that economic growth is the mechanism that leads to a long-term increase in national output based on the criteria above.

The relationship between foreign direct investment and economic growth

If a country wishes to prosper economically, it must set aside and invest a sufficient portion of its gross domestic product. Developing countries, on the other hand, are poor by definition, with low savings and investment rates, contributing to their persistent poverty. Foreign resources are expected to supplement domestic resources and contribute to the economy's growth. For developing countries, foreign direct investment is viewed as a critical tool for achieving economic success. Foreign direct investment is seen to benefit the host country's economic development in a variety of ways, both direct and indirect. It encourages domestic investment, which is critical for long-term growth and development (Newfarmer & Sztajerowska, 2012). Another researcher by (Borensztein, De Gregorio, & Lee, 1998) believes that FDI is an important channel for technology transfer that leads to faster growth than local investment. Some of the channels identified include increased capital accumulation in the recipient economy, improved efficiency of locally owned host country firms via contract and demonstration effects, and their exposure to fierce competition, technological change, human capital augmentation, and increased exports. On the other hand, the extent to which FDI contributes to growth is influenced by the recipient country's economic and social status, or, in other words, the nature of its environment (Buckley, Clegg, & Wang, 2002).

Several empirical research on the causal relationship between FDI and development have been conducted. Several studies have identified evidence of technological spillover and increased plant productivity at the corporate level. FDI inflows into industrialized countries appear to 'crowd in' other investments and are associated to an increase in overall investment at the macro level. Most studies have connected FDI inflows to higher per capita GDP, quicker economic growth rates, and higher productivity growth. In empirical investigations, higher host country exports and stronger backward and forward ties with multinational affiliates were discovered as other ways that FDI boosted growth. According to the paper, the amount of FDI that contributes to economic growth is governed by the recipient country's economic and social characteristics, as well as the nature of the environment. This suggests that the economy's quality is linked to the host country's savings rate, transparency, and technological growth, all of which would help the host countries' economies benefit from more FDI. Giving to (Lee, 1998) regard FDI as a substantial technology transfer vehicle that, as compared to local investment, significantly contributes to growth. According to (Izuchukwu, 1886) Foreign direct investment has been one of the most important ways for raising funds into various areas of the economy (FDI). In both developed and developing countries, a profusion of empirical research has been undertaken on the relationship between foreign direct investment and economic progress. The causes of both growth and FDI, the engagement of Trans-National Companies (TNCs) in host nations, and the direction of causation between the two variables were revealed through unraveling this nexus.

Impact of FDI on economic growth and development in Nigeria

Several studies have been undertaken in Nigeria on the relationship between foreign direct investment and economic growth. For instance, (Edozie.E.G, 1995) The influence of foreign direct investment on the Nigerian economy was discussed, and it was decided that these effects had not been considered, and that the wide linkage effects were lower than the Chenery-Watanabe average. Again, (John, 2016) the research looked at the factors that drove FDI flows into Nigeria before and during the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP), and found that the macro policies in place before to SAP were limiting investors. The multiplication and growth of parallel markets, as well as continuous capital flight, came from this policy climate. An further empirical result by (Okonkwo, Egbunike, & Udeh, 2015) discovered that FDI is positively correlated with GDP and concluded that larger FDI inflows would result in better economic performance for the country, whereas lower FDI inflows would result in worse economic performance for the country (Olokoyo, 2012) evaluated the effects of FDI on the Nigerian economy and concluded that they were insufficient. In Nigeria, public investment has had a negative contribution to GDP growth (Oyatoye, Arogundade, Adebisi, & Oluwakayode, 2011).

Empirical studies on the relationship between FDI and economic growth

Previous studies exploring the relationship between FDI and economic growth in Nigeria and other countries produced mixed results. According to actual research findings, foreign direct investment benefits host countries' economies. A study of the impact of foreign direct investment on economic growth has been carried out. Their findings showed that foreign direct investment had a major impact on Nigeria's economic growth (Ehimare, 2011; Ojeaburu, 2019; Olokoyo, 2012; Oyatoye et al., 2011).

Also, (Adamu, Kabuga, & Suleiman, 2015) researchers looked at the impact of foreign private investment on economic growth using annual time-series data from the Nigerian economy. The paper employed co-integration and Error Correction Mechanism (ECM) approaches to empirically analyze the relationship between foreign private investment and economic development and to make policy implications on the found association. Earlier disequilibria between long-run economic growth and foreign private investment, according to the study, resulted in significant feedback of 116 percent and 78 percent, respectively. The researchers looked at the influence of FDI on growth in 25 transition economies in Central and Eastern Europe and the former Soviet Union. In these countries, FDI was only for the purpose of technology transfer. Foreign direct investment has a strong favorable impact on the economic development of each of the countries investigated, according to their findings. This finding supports the notion that foreign direct investment (FDI) corresponds to technology transfer that benefits the host country. Another study found that when the host country's education reaches a certain level, the beneficial effect of FDI on growth is doubled. FDI has a greater influence on growth in countries that adopt an export promotion strategy rather than an import substitution program (V. N. Balasubramanyam, and, & Sapsford, 1996).

Besides, (Olokoyo, 2012) the impact of foreign direct investment (FDI) on Nigeria's economic development was studied. The goal of the research was to find an answer to the following question: What are the elements that influence foreign direct investment in Nigeria, and how do they effect the economy? The researchers employed the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression technique to look at the time series data from 1970 to 2007. The Cochrane-Orcutt iterative technique was used to correct for autocorrelation. In Nigeria's economic development, the model implies that real gross domestic product (RGDP) and foreign direct investment (FDI) have a functional connection. From 1969 to 2000, time-series data for Chile, Malaysia, and Thailand are used to investigate the causal relationship between FDI and economic growth. In this experiment, the Toda and Yamamoto causality test was used. In Chile, GDP affects FDI but not the other way around, but in Malaysia and Thailand, there is considerable evidence of bi-directional causality between the two variables (Hansen & Rand, 2006).

Several studies on Nigerian investment and growth have been carried out, with varying outcomes and submissions. In their research of the factors that influence FDI in Nigeria, they found that (Ajibola et al., 2019;

Akinyemi A. Ajibolaa, A., & Adeyemid, 2018). Changes in domestic investment, output or market size, indigenization policy, and economic openness have all been highlighted as major FDI variables. The extent, trajectory, and prospects of FDI in Nigeria were evaluated, and it was concluded that while the FDI regime in Nigeria was improving, it still had some significant faults. The majority of these faults are related to the business environment (such as corporate law, bankruptcy, labor law, and so on), as well as institutional instability and the rule of law. It also stated that there is a large body of literature demonstrating the link between foreign direct investment (FDI) and economic development, particularly in transitional societies, and that FDI is defined as a series of investments made to acquire a long-term interest in companies operating outside the investor's economy. For example, foreign direct investment (FDI) is a type of equity loan or finance in which the investor has a stake in the company (Basu & Srinivasan, 2002).

Empirical studies on the relationship between FDI and employment growth

FDI helps to increase the quantity and quality of jobs available. Unemployment is a big problem in developing countries. As a result, the employment generation effect of FDI is crucial for countries to reduce their unemployment rates. According to the 2006 World Investment Report of the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD, 2006a). The majority of FDI from developed countries to emerging economies is capital- or technology-intensive, resulting in a crowding-out effect on the economies of recipient countries. Some researchers determined that FDI had a positive impact on employment after analyzing the relationship between FDI and employment, whereas others disagree. The following is a more detailed examination of this issue of debate. But more importantly, (Mpanju, 2012; Mpanju.A.K, 2012) the ordinary least squares technique to statistical model building and analysis was used to study the relationship between employment as the dependent variable and FDI as the independent variable in Tanzania. His findings found a clear positive relationship between the two variables, implying that higher FDI inflows were linked to increased employment. Research position by (Nunnenkamp & Bremont, 2007) the relationship between foreign direct investment (FDI) and employment statistics from approximately 200 Mexican industrial businesses was investigated. They discovered that FDI had a significant positive impact on manufacturing employment, albeit in a limited way. Both white-collar and blue-collar jobs were affected by their findings. When crowding-out is taken into consideration, however, some studies indicate that the impact of FDI on employment is insignificant. When foreign multinational businesses concentrate on the market of the recipient country, the crowding-out impact is significant. The crowding-out effect of FDI will result in more domestic companies going bankrupt and more local employees being laid off because the influx of FDI will put more pressure on domestic firms, and because the advanced technologies and higher productivity associated with foreign investment will require fewer workers than before. Empirical findings by (Mack Shelley, Kelly, & Yu, 2013) argued that the impact of foreign direct investment on employment in European countries varied depending on the country's economic development stage, making predictions problematic. He assumed that the first-level impact of FDI on employment was characterized by creative destruction, implying that unproductive jobs would depart

immediately after new and more productive occupations appeared. There is a lot of competition created by the capitalism process and the transition from a controlled to a market economy. International investors modified their production mode before local firms in order to make more money. Thus, the extensive use of machinery and labor division caused more current employees to lose their jobs and in this process, a more productive workforce was also generated by international companies (Sharma & Kaur, 2013). The ruling class and managers began to regulate the workers, and factories began to rely on computers. Labor-intensive investment promotes further jobs at a later stage and converts creative destruction into a beneficial impact on employment. Furthermore, according to (Dufaux, 2010), greenfield investment has a favorable influence on jobs, while brownfield investment, combined with the privatization trend that creates a dynamic market economy, has a weak positive impact on employment. This research shows that FDI is not a magic bullet for job development. FDI pushes out small and medium-sized domestic firms and produces mass unemployment in domestic enterprises, the fast growth of FDI in Latin American countries throughout the 1990s has had little effect on employment (Ernst, 2005a). Foreign direct investment has a positive impact on the service industry. They divided FDI into three types: resource-seeking FDI, efficiency-seeking FDI, and market-seeking FDI, and compared the international mobility costs of FDI producers and users to analyze the job consequences of FDI. Market-seeking FDI will dominate the local labor market and have a neutral or positive impact if customers are immobile or have significant transportation costs," they concluded. If users' mobility costs are low, FDI-seeking resources and productivity will take priority, wreaking havoc on the domestic labor market (Wei, 2013a).

Materials and methods

This chapter discusses the research methodologies employed in this study. The study region and population, sample strategies, data collection techniques, and data analysis methodologies are all described. A variety of data gathering approaches have been used to investigate the impact of foreign direct investment (FDI) on employment in Nigeria. The study employed a survey design. Respondents were chosen at random to get a sense of how they felt about foreign aid administration. Closed-ended questions were employed in the questionnaires (Likert scale). Our example frame includes the Nigerian Central Bank, the Federal Ministries of Finance, Trade, Industries, and Investment, the Small and Medium Scale Development Agency, the Chamber of Commerce and Industry, the National President, and the Nigerian Manufacturing Association. Both primary and secondary data were used, although data analysis was done with primary data. For data processing and analysis, SPSS version 25 was utilized, with the linear multiple regression model, ANOVA, and Durbin Watson test used to determine reality. The technical path for this investigation was an exploratory study with an institutional survey design. As a result, the researcher was able to use questions to elicit comments from persons who were well-versed in the issue. The research strategy was suitable for reaching the survey objectives and addressing the research questions (Cooper, Schindler, & Sun, 2006). This is a qualitative research method that is utilized to acquire a better knowledge of FDI and job creation difficulties. Data on FDI and its effects on job creation came from institutional managers, supervisors, and accountants on purpose. The collected data was put

through a thematic analysis.

Modelling, Methodological Framework, and Data Analysis

This paper examined the impact of foreign direct investment on employment in Nigeria. The analysis in the Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) model followed a well-established pattern. After estimating descriptive statistics for six (6) variables.

The general form of our empirical multiple regression model is as follows:

$$FDI = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 EG + \beta_2 GR + \beta_3 IT + \beta_4 LS + \beta_5 EC + \varepsilon$$

Where;

FDI=Foreign Direct Investment

EG=Economic Growth

α =Trend/Constant

β =Coefficients

GR=Government Revenue

IT=Increased Tax

LS=Living standard

EC=Employment Creation

ε =Error of term

Discussion of the result of the study

Descriptive Statistics of Respondents

The results are shown in table (1) specifies the descriptive statistics of our respondents. The data for this research was gathered from five core areas in Nigeria; namely the Central Bank of Nigeria, Ministry of the external affairs, Ministry of Finance, Trade, Industries and Investment, and Small and Medium Scale Development Agency.

From the data obtained, most of our respondents were males, which account for 69% whereas 31% were females. This is an indication that most men are actively involved in pursuing the economic agenda of Nigeria. Again, 15 percent of our respondents were between the ages of 31 and 40, 35 percent were between the ages of 41 and 50, 17 percent were between the ages of 20 and 30, 22 percent were between the ages of 51 and 60, and 10 percent were over 60. This shows that a higher percentage of 35 of our respondents were within the working

population were duly considered as part of the research. Hence, valid data were gathered from the respondents to form the basis and justification for the research. 14% of our respondents have a Ph.D., followed by a master's degree accounting for 42% and 44% representing respondents with Bachelor's degree. This is also an indication that a higher percentage of the respondents have graduated from tertiary institutions and are actively involved in ensuring the inflow of FDI and its implication on economic development. The findings from the descriptive statistics show that a higher percentage of our respondents are married which accounted for 49%, 21% are single, whereas 11% and 20% are divorced and widowed respectively. This is an indication that the married category has to work hard to gain income to cater to their families.

More importantly, the field survey shows that a higher percentage of 70 of our responses were gathered from top managerial positions whereas 7% and 23% play accountant and supervisory roles. This is an indication that required information was gathered from the right sources to justify the credibility of the research findings.

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics for the Sample. N= 292

Variables		Frequency	Percent
Name of Firm (Valid)	Central Bank of Nigeria	120	41
	Ministry of external affair	33	11
	Ministry of finance	56	19
	Trade, Industries, and Investment	44	15
	Small and Medium Scale Development Agency	39	13
Gender (Valid)	Female	90	31
	Male	202	69
Age (Valid)	20-30	51	17
	31-40	44	15
	41-50	103	35
	51-60	64	22
	60+	30	10
Marital Status (Valid)	Single	62	21
	Married	144	49
	Divorced	28	11
	Widowed	58	20
Educational Level (Valid)	PhD	41	14
	Masters	123	42
	Bachelors/Others	128	44
Business role (Valid)	Accountant	20	7

	Supervisory	68	23
	Managerial	204	70
Total		292	100

Field survey, (2021)

Table 2 gives a reflection on the statistical description of the variables, the results show that the variables are not wider apart from themselves. The same samples were arrived at. In terms of values, the minimum values, maximum values, mean values, and standard deviations are practically identical. This means that the variable is not wider dispersed from the mean. The variables generally show low standard deviation values.

Table 2 Statistical Description of all Variables applied in the Data Analysis

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
FDI	292	1	5	4.104	0.809
EG	292	1	5	4.079	0.833
GR	292	1	5	4.110	0.770
IT	292	1	5	4.131	0.711
LS	292	1	5	4.137	0.755
EC	292	1	5	4.137	0.755

Field Survey, 2021

Table 3 Test for Reliability

variables	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
FDI	0.849	4
EG	0.904	4
GR	0.829	4
IT	0.813	4
LS	0.818	4
EC	0.818	4

Field Survey, 2021

Table 3 shows the extent to which the data for the study can reproduce similar results when a similar methodological approach is applied. Hence in research, a reliability test indicates that the data used must regenerate or repeat the same results when a similar approach is used. For example, a scale or test is said to be trustworthy if its measurement yields the same result when repeated under the same conditions (Golafshani, 2003). Testing for dependability is important since it pertains to the consistency of a measuring instrument's parts (Golafshani, 2003). As a result, Cronbach's Alpha was utilized as a measure of internal consistency and reliability. Cronbach's Alpha is a reliability coefficient that shows how well elements in a data collection are positively associated. Cronbach's alpha tests were used to determine the reliability of the multiple-question Likert scale questionnaires. More importantly, Cronbach Alpha measures the inter-correlation among internal

consistency and reliability of the test items were greater with a score of one (1). But mostly the acceptable measurement is set to fall within 0.7 to 0.9 (Landau & Everitt, 2003). However, our outcome of the test result in table 3 shows that the estimated Cronbach Alpha for all scale of measurement variables is justified within the measurement of constructs of 0.7 to 0.9 which simply implies a high correlation between the items and the questions set for the survey. The value is an indication that our questionnaire used for the study has satisfied the reliability test.

Validity test

Validity in research establishes whether a study accurately measures what it was designed to measure and the accuracy of the investigation's findings. According to (Golafshani, 2003), construct validity is a term used in research to describe the validity of a study. The construct is the original thought, query, or hypothesis that guides which data should be collected and how it should be collected. The supervisor double-checked all of the questions. The goal is to ensure that the instrument is adequate and representative of all of the variables being measured. Before the final administration of the data instrument to collect data for the research, we pre-tested its validity and reliability. A pilot test was conducted using thirty-eight (38) respondents from various departments to determine the accuracy and validity of the instruments before gathering final data for the study. This aided us to modify the research instrument making it clear to understand and eliminate the uncertainty of items before the final distribution.

Table 4 Pearson's Correlation Coefficient: Correlation matrix

		FDI	EG	GR	IT	LS	EC
FDI	Pearson Correlation	1					
	Sig. (2-tailed)						
	N	292					
EG	Pearson Correlation	.577**	1				
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000					
	N	292	292				
GR	Pearson Correlation	.605**	.425**	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000				
	N	292	292	292			
IT	Pearson Correlation	.675**	.775**	.394**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000			
	N	292	292	292	292		
LS	Pearson Correlation	.808**	.593**	.559**	.810**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000		
	N	292	292	292	292	292	
EC	Pearson Correlation	.807**	.595**	.558**	.810**	.999**	1

Note **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4 divulges the matrix of correlation of the estimated variables of concern. Although most of the construct items significantly correlated among themselves, EC correlated strongly with LS (.999**) whereas

LS strongly correlated with IT (.810**) at a 1% significant level. We, therefore, accepted that there is a strong relationship between EC, LS, and IT. This indicates that the inflow of FDI will affect employment creation and living standard of people and eventually lead to an increase in the tax base of the economy because people will get work to do, pay their tax and raise their living standards. Although, other researchers such as (Rizvi & Nishat, 2009) concluded their study of the impact of FDI on employment opportunities in India, China, and Pakistan, by stating that it would not suffice to expect FDI to create a direct impact on employment opportunities in the above-mentioned countries. They also suggest that in addition to FDI enhancement policies, other measures to boost employment growth should be generated. Again, the matrix shows that FDI correlated with LS (.808**) at a 1% significant level. The result suggests that FDI and LS have a relationship that will consequently impact employment creation through the inflow of FDI. However, all construct items have established a statistically significant relationship amongst themselves. But revealingly, the inflow of FDI and its effect on employment creation will positively impact LS and IT.

Regression Analysis

Durbin Watson statistic test

The sample adequacy was determined using the Durbin Watson statistic test for variable model analysis. In the residuals of statistical regression analysis, we looked for autocorrelation. The value of the Durbin-Watson statistic will always be between 0 and 4. However, a value of 2.000 was obtained in this example, showing a positive autocorrelation.

Table 5 Model Summary

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change in R Square	F Change	df1	df2	Sig.	Durbin-Watson
.999a	0.999	0.998	0.029	0.999	38256	5	286	0	2.009702

a. Predictors: (Constant), LS, GR, EG, FDI, IT

b. Dependent Variable: EC

According to table 5, the R-value of .999 indicates a high level of prediction. The R square value of .999 indicates that our independent variable explains 99.9 percent of the variability in our dependent variable (employment creation). As a result, factors other than the predictors included in this model account for 1 percent (100 percent -99 percent) of the variation. The adjusted R square value of 0.998 shows that the independent factors explain 99 percent of the variation in the outcome variable.

Table 6 ANOVA Test.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	165.160	5	33.032	38256.121*	.000b
Residual	0.247	286	0.001		
Total	165.407	291			

a. Dependent Variable: EC

b. Predictors: (Constant), LS, GR, EG, FDI, IT

The analysis of variance was tested using two or more factors to compare the variables in table 6. The total regression model was checked for a fair fit for the data using the F-ratio in the ANOVA (Table 6). From the table, the series of residual point values of difference is 286 whereas the series of residual point's sum of squares value is 165.407. The independent variable is statistically significant in predicting the dependent variables, as evidenced by this, $F(5, 286) = 38256.121^*$, $p(.000) < .05$ (the regression model fits the data well.).

Table 7 Standardized Coefficients values (Multiple Regression)

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.	Correlations			Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error				Zero-order	Partial	Part	Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	0.007	0.012		0.615	0.539					
FDI	-0.002	0.004	-0.002*	-0.441	0.659	0.807	-0.026	-0.001	0.303	3.299*
EG	0.003	0.003	0.003*	0.798	0.425	0.595	0.047	0.002	0.358	2.796*
GR	-0.001	0.003	-0.001*	-0.213	0.831	0.558	-0.013	0.000	0.576	1.736*
IT	0.000	0.005	0.000*	0.015	0.988	0.810	0.001	0.000	0.195	5.134*
LS	0.997	0.005	0.999*	193.466	0.000	0.999	0.996	0.442	0.196	5.110*

a. Dependent Variable: EC

Table 7 illustrates the statistical significance of the dependent variable on the independent variable. Employment creation positively affects living standards. This indicates that a percentage change in the employment creation will lead to a 99.9% increase in living standard at $p(0.00) < 0.05$. This indicates that a percentage change in the LS will lead to a 99.9% increase in employment creation in Nigeria. However, FDI is statistically not significant, according to the test results at $p(.659) > 0.05$. Again, EG, GR and IT are statistically not significant at $p(0.425) > 0.05$, at $p(0.831) > 0.05$, and $p(0.988) > 0.05$ respectively. This indicates that FDI is not impacting positively on EC. These research findings are in line with (Ozughalu & Ogwumike, 2013). The collinearity with variance inflation values, on the other hand, is all less than 10. The result indicates that there is no multi-collinearity diagnostic in the data set.

Table 8 Residuals Statistics

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	1.000	4.999	4.135	0.753	292
Residual	-0.494	0.015	0.000	0.029	292
Std. Predicted Value	-4.161	1.147	0.000	1.000	292
Std. Residual	-16.808	0.497*	0.000	0.991	292

a. Dependent Variable: EC

The predicted variables on the dependent variable in Table 8 have a standard residual value of 0.497, which indicates that the data set is normally distributed. The usual residual value exceeds -3 to 3 when plotted. However, a maximum value of 4.999, shows the impact of the predicted value on the dependent variable (EC).

Conclusion

The study was based on four (4) objectives to find out the empirical and causal relationship existing between foreign direct investment, economic growth, government revenue, increased tax, living standard, and employment creation in the Nigerian economy.

To better understand the importance and mutual relationship that exist between these variables, five departments of interest were purposively selected to investigate and ascertain the influence of foreign direct investment, economic growth, government revenue, increased tax, living standard on employment creation, and how important it to factor them into economic growth. This will help strategize and device innovative ways of channeling the inflows to boost the economy and sustain employment, and further develop innovative economic strategies to boost economic prosperity. Hence, having a pre-requisite knowledge on foreign direct investment, economic growth, government revenue, increased tax, and living standard and its application will help determine its success on employment creation in every economy. The negativity of the statistical variables (independent variables) then determines how insignificant these variables are on the dependent variable (employment creation). The result of this research is an important contribution to the existing knowledge on FDI. The results disclose that hypotheses (H1, H2, H3, and H4) have established the following results: Foreign direct investment is statistically not significant on employment creation. Economic growth is not statistically significant in employment creation. Government revenue generation through foreign direct investment does not impact positively on employment creation and an increased tax revenue does not impact positively on employment creation respectively. The test result is an indication that foreign direct investment received into the Nigerian economy is not impacting significantly on employment creation. The reverse of this will certainly widen the unemployment gap in the country.

Generally, our findings bring to bear that the Nigerian economy received the inflow of foreign investment into the country. But its positive impact on employment creation to close the unemployment gap persists. However, the positive correlation established between the variables is an indication that when FDI impact positively on employment creation, this will eventually affect economic growth, government revenue, increased tax, and the living standard of the people positively. The application of these research findings could be used as a guide and the need to utilize the foreign direct inflows received for employment creation to ease or close the unemployment gap in Nigeria. This will help in boosting the economic prosperity of nations.

We, therefore conclude that countries receive some form of foreign direct investment, yet unemployment is still a problem to deal with in Nigeria and Africa as a whole. Hence, we ask the question of what has accounted for the persistence of unemployment in Africa. This is a research gap that can further be investigated to ascertain reality.

Managerial implications and conclusion

To ensure that foreign direct investment positively affects employment creation in Nigeria, government departments and agencies responsible for ensuring economic prosperity should monitor closely and evaluate its effects on employment and other variables such as economic growth, government revenue, increased tax, and living standard to ascertain whether there is a significant positive change in these variables of constructs. This will help track the progress of the economy and pull in appropriate investment opportunities to aid economic prosperity. Thereby enhancing, sustaining, and developing best strategies and practices. It will also help in identifying factors of consideration for business appraisal and economic development. In a broader sense, the Keynesian theory of employment is more preferred over other theories. The level of employment in the short term, according to Keynes, depends on the aggregate effective demand for goods in the region. The higher the aggregate efficient demand, the greater the employment volume, and vice versa. Unemployment, according to Keynes, the product of a lack of effective demand. This means that the volume of jobs created through foreign direct investment is an avenue for bridging the unemployment gap. Hence, we position our research in support of this theory as a best practice.

Limitations and future research

Despite the pandemic the world is battling with (COVID-19), the researcher tried everything possible to engage respondents to offer their best in eliciting responses for the study. Although, there was time limitation and financial constraint to meet transportation cost of data collection. The research established strong policy support for research and development to set the tone for the economic growth, development, and prosperity of nations. This will enhance and sustain countries and place them at a competitive advantage to face world crises as and when necessary. It will help develop a further innovative economic strategy from the construct variables that have statistical relevance on the dependent variable (employment creation). The additional study can be carried out in other parts of the world by combining other variables such as population growth, and the structure of the population which were not included in our hypotheses can be tested to ascertain its significance on employment creation.

Innovation of the paper

The study aimed at supporting the inflow of FDI and employment creation; since it has both positive and negative impacts on employment and other variables such as economic growth, government revenue, increased tax, and living standard. This paper, therefore, brings to bear that inflows of FDI are less significant to impact greatly on employment. Therefore, there is the possibility of unemployment persisting in the country. There is compelling empirical evidence that FDI is not impacting positively to reflect on economic growth, government revenue, increased tax, and living standard. However, if the impact is positive, it will also establish a positive impact on the estimated variables such as economic growth, government revenue, increased tax, and the living standard of the people. If it does, will help maximize productivity and reduce unemployment hunger, and raise

the living standard of the people. Hence, the adoption and application of this concept will help in the success of the economic agenda of nations. At present, no such specific work has been done in Nigeria to the extent of regressing and testing these variables and developing a graphical abstract or framework. This propelled our interest to investigate and established reality. Hence, an area of concern that needs attention for policy formation by focusing on its impact on employment creation.

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